

INFLUENCE OF INNOVATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING A
FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Annotation: *This paper examines the role of new teaching strategies and methods in to the classroom, and learn effect of this methods in learners. Moreover it gives information about innovative teaching methods and their benefits for the student learning process and attitude.*

Key words: *innovative methods, psychological approach, multimedia resources, demonstrate aspects, analysis .*

As in every other sphere, education is developing rapidly and opening new opportunities for schoolchildren. Nowadays, many European educational institutions are using unique methods and learning programs in their daily activities. With the help of various multimedia resources, there are more possibilities to make students interested in a certain subject or demonstrate aspects of it to them in more detail. Innovative teaching methods do not only refer to the technological part used in class. A psychological approach and an analysis of children's behavior and perception of the information they receive are also important for discussing this work. It appears that some educational methodologies have a tremendous impact on the development of students.

The use of multimedia remains one of the most popular innovative teaching methods and tools used in the primary school at the moment. When children interact with computers, electronic gadgets, and other technologies, they can gain a better experience with subjects that are described in books . Such materials as video, audio, and text files become available for teachers who use them throughout the learning course, as well as for children who have a better perception of the

provided information through all the visual aids mentioned above . Moreover, it is necessary to develop learning courses with the integration of such pedagogical approaches as phenomenon-based learning, co-teaching, portfolio creation, mind maps, Z-A approach, and others.

Innovation in education can lead to better overall outcomes in the school environment. Innovative classrooms are filled with students who are developing stronger communication skills and building engagement capacity amongst their peers. Personalized learning and differentiated opportunities for students due to innovative practices in education are key components to preparing students for a global, competitive workforce in the 21st century. In this digital age, students learning in innovative classrooms can potentially retain more information and process at a deeper level of understanding.

Using innovative methods of teaching is a crucial skill for teachers and education staff. Scientific research has shown that innovative teaching methods and approaches can significantly enhance the student learning process.

Some of our most inspiring and unforgettable movies are of teachers and professors who use innovative methods of teaching to reach out to the minds of the students and win the hearts of the audience while doing so. While a few years ago, one would only see such innovative and effective teaching on the screen, today technology has given teachers across the world a number of tools to enhance teaching methods.

Here are some innovative teaching strategies which every teacher can embrace and make their teaching way more interesting:

Cross over Teaching

While this form of teaching does not include technology, it is an enriching experience for the student as well as the faculty. Here, the learning happens in an informal setting such as after-school learning clubs, or trips to museums and exhibition. The teacher can link the educational content with the experiences that the students are having. This teaching is further enhanced and deepened by adding

questions related to the subject. The students can then add to the classroom discussions through field trip notes, photographic projects and other group assignments related to the trip.

Teaching through Flipping Classrooms

Flipping the classroom is becoming an increasingly popular effective teaching method. In this technique, the students are made active participants of the learning process by passing the onus of learning on them, it requires the teachers to relegate to the role of resource providers and the students take the responsibility of gathering concepts information. Using various tools of technology the students are encouraged to constructing knowledge, fill in the information gaps and make inferences on their own as and when needed.

While many may question if giving students the responsibility of learning may world, it has been seen by teachers across the world that when put in charge of their own learning they immerse themselves more in the subject, taking more interest and learning better.

This method of teaching is one of the best ways to lay the foundation in independent learning.

Learner-Centred Instruction (LCI)

In contrast to traditional teaching methods, new techniques allow for two-way dialogue. Students can share their thoughts on a subject, and mistakes can be corrected right away. It is the teacher's job to guide and support the exploration of student ideas.

Enhancement of Analytical Skills

For the student to learn independently, the instructor serves as a facilitator in the classroom. By synthesizing the material provided by the teacher, he increases his level of topic knowledge. In the same way as a jigsaw puzzle, the student assembles all components. As a result, he progresses from basic to more detailed understanding.

Incubates and nurtures thinking process

With innovative instructional methods, students are given fresh themes to discuss and collect data. High-order thinking (HOT) abilities are developed due to this continuous process. Having the capacity to think beyond the box is a benefit to students.

Improves the ability to compare

In contrast to the previous one, the new teaching technique gives students real-world experiences. Learning to distinguish between theory and application is the goal of these classes.

Conclusion. The quality in the classroom is based on planning lessons and courses, understanding learners, managing this lesson, knowing the subject, managing resources, assessing learning, interacting ICT, taking responsibility for professional development, using inclusive practices, promoting 21st century skills and understanding educational policies and practice.

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